

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****CHILD BEHAVIOR DURING DENTAL TREATMENT, AND ITS
ASSESSMENT**

Torki mree alqahtani, Bandar abdullah alawad, Ali salem alharthi,
Zohair masood Alghamdi, Somaya abdukarim Alghamdi, Fahad muawwadh
algethami, Nasser awad alamri, Majed meshal Alharbi, Amr omair alotaibi,
Fares saleh alshubrumi

Abstract:

Dental anxiousness is multifactorial and much more complicated than can be described by a solitary contributing element. A child's habits in oral situation is an outcome of interconnected relationships in between personal characteristics and situational and ecological elements. In this review we discuss the most common factors affecting the behavior and cooperativity of the patient during dental treatment, and also assessment methods of a dentist of this condition. We performed a search using electronic databases; MEDLINE, and EMBASE, through October, 2019. Search strategies used following MeSH terms in searching: "pediatric dentistry", "child oral health", "children behavior", "management".

Corresponding author:**Torki mree alqahtani,**

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Torki mree alqahtani et al., Child Behavior During Dental Treatment, And Its Assessment., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).**

INTRODUCTION:

In 1986, when the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry recommended that the very first dental visit of a child should happen at around 6 months old, the number of professionals providing dental care to youngsters has greatly escalated ^[1]. This very early care is justified not just in terms of the upkeep of oral health, however also because it permits the kid to get utilized to regular oral procedures ^[2]. Nevertheless, the emotional aspects of dental care at this age have been hardly any examined.

Knowledge about early youth psychological advancement is basic for the comprehending of behavioral elements associated with oral care at this age. The overlook of behavioral reactions of youngsters to standard dental stimuli permits the building of distinctive behavioral patterns. In kids taken into consideration to be "normal," the method often used to describe behavioral patterns is their combination with the youngster's age based on the principles of psychosocial and psychomotor growth widely reported in the psychology literary works. Basing on to Rud and Kisling, chronologic and mental age have a substantial influence upon the moment taken for kids to approve oral therapy ^[3].

Klein states that the way the child absorbs its experience with the dental practitioner is decisive for the development of mindsets and assumptions toward oral therapy, although the emotional influence of oral therapy began during early childhood is not precisely known ^[2].

Dental anxiousness is multifactorial and much more complicated than can be described by a solitary contributing element. A child's habits in oral situation is an outcome of interconnected relationships in between personal characteristics and situational and ecological elements. In this review we discuss the most common factors affecting the behavior and cooperativity of the patient during dental treatment, and also assessment methods of a dentist of this condition.

METHODOLOGY:

We performed a search using electronic databases; MEDLINE, and EMBASE, through October, 2019. Search strategies used following MeSH terms in

searching: "pediatric dentistry", "child oral health", "children behavior", "management". Then we also searched the bibliographies of included studies for further relevant references to our review. Studies had to be relevant to our criteria which should be review, systematic reviews, or clinical studies restriction to only English language published articles with human subject were applied in our search strategies.

DISCUSSION:**• FACTORS AFFECTING THE BEHAVIOR OF THE CHILD****Development status**

An area of factor to consider is the child's developmental standing (Table 2). As children establish from immaturity to youth, their cooperative capacities likewise transform. Along with understanding the age of a youngster patient, the dental practitioner must analyze his or her physical development, degree of socializing, capacity to function separately, intellectual development, and linguistic capability. All these aspects offer a sign of the behavior maturity of the youngster.

It is necessary to review the regular actions and advancement of anxieties (consisting of DFA (Dental fear and anxiety)) in child patients considering their age, learned actions patterns and managing stress and anxieties as a result of far better understanding of patients' actions throughout dental therapy.

Table 1 reveals series of look of different anxieties in children from newborn/infant to adolescent age ^[4]. It is revealed that these concerns, showing up in every duration till begin of puberty, can be straight or indirectly pertaining to the components of oral office (the environment, personnel, sounds, noises and smells, instruments, distress, etc.). These are precise reasons that the DFA (dental fear and anxiousness) has one of the most common start in child age, established in one of the Rachman devices ^[4]. Liddel and Gosse performed a research concerning existence of unpleasant dental experiences in individuals and they determined that those kinds of experiences took place in 90% of situations before 15th year of life of patients who reported experiencing of undesirable oral scenarios ^[5].

Table 1. Types of fears in infant, child and adolescent period.

Age	Types of fears
0-6 months	loud noises; loss of physical support
6-18 months	strangers; unknown situations; separation from parents; sudden and unexpected objects
2-3 years	animals; darkness; imaginary creations
3-6 years	darkness; storms; loss of close persons; body injuries
6-10 years	school; concern; darkness; body injuries and physical danger; loneliness; insects; supernatural beings
10-12 years	socialization; physical appearance; thunders and lightning
13-18 years	socialization; rejection from surroundings; physical appearance

DBP (dental behavior problems) that could appear in the dental office are simply the indication of organic responses turned on after contact with the nerve-wracking variables able to cause DFA. DBP is specified as uncooperative behavior in the dental office, which results in slow-going of therapy or no doing it whatsoever. Prevalence of DBP is about 9-10.5% in kid and adolescent populace [6]. DBP represents multifactorial design made up of individual (age, gender, temperament, emotional and habits troubles, cultural inheritance, basic worry and stress and anxiety presence, etc.) and situational variables (experience of distress and unpleasantness in the oral office, lack of control, improper dental practitioner behavior, etc.) [6].

Table 2. Developmental stages for children and adolescents [7].

Sensorimotor period Age 0 to 2 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unable to reason • Reality is external • No object permanence • Reacts to stress with senses • Element of amnesia 0 to 2 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unable to reason • Reality is external • No object permanence • Reacts to stress with senses • Element of amnesia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A period of consolidation; deliberate • Takes pride in possessions • Plays cooperatively with peers • Relinquishing comfort objects Age 5 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A period of consolidation; deliberate • Takes pride in possessions • Plays cooperatively with peers • Relinquishing comfort objects
Preoperative period Age 2 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geared to gross motor skills • Likes to see and touch • Very attached to parent • Solitary play; rarely shares • Limited vocabulary; early sentence formation • Becoming interested in self-help skills Age 2 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geared to gross motor skills • Likes to see and touch • Very attached to parent • Solitary play; rarely shares • Limited vocabulary; early sentence formation • Becoming interested in self-help skills 	Age 6 to 13 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eager to learn • Discriminates, classifies • Cause-and-effect logic • Begins to trust • Internal organization (conceptualization) • Recognizes and understands pain
Age 3 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less egocentric; likes to please • Very active imagination; likes stories • Remains closely attached to parent 	Age 13 to 17 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can deal with abstract • Can solve complex problems • Reasons inductively • Developing ideals and attitudes Age 13 to 17 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can deal with abstract • Can solve complex problems

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reasons inductively • Developing ideals and attitudes |
|--|

Dental Caries

In literature, the association between dental caries and dental anxiety has been investigated [3,5,15]. This association could be true in both directions. Indeed, this means that high caries prevalence in a child may lead to increased anxiety towards visiting a dentist, and the presence of dental anxiety may lead to avoidance of dental check-ups, which would result in an increased prevalence of dental caries [29,30]. Most previous studies found that dental anxiety is related to caries prevalence and is considered a risk factor for dental caries [3,5,15,34]. However, a few studies reported that dental anxiety is not related to dental caries prevalence, and is rather influenced by other factors [35,36].

Dental Caries and Pain

In literature, the combination between tooth decays and dental anxiety has indeed been investigated [8]. This association could be true in both trajectories. Undoubtedly, this suggests that high caries occurrence in a youngster may cause increased stress and anxiety in the direction of seeing a dentist, and the visibility of dental stress and anxiety might result in evasion of dental check-ups, which would cause an enhanced frequency of cavities [9]. Most previous research studies discovered that oral stress and anxiety is associated with decays prevalence and is taken into consideration a risk element for cavities [8], [9]. Nonetheless, a few researches reported that dental anxiousness is not connected to tooth decays frequency and is instead influenced by various other elements [10].

Pain has a direct influence on behavior [2]. Findings of pain or an uncomfortable previous healthcare visit are important considerations in the patient's medical/dental history that will certainly aid the dental expert expect possible habits issues [10]. Furthermore, pain evaluation and management during pediatric dental treatments are important as pain has a direct impact on actions. Prevention or reduction of pain during treatment can support the relationship between the dentist and the patient, construct trust, lessen concern and anxiousness, and improve positive dental perspectives for future visits.

Time duration

Therapy duration is a central situational element which creates deterioration of children's behavior throughout or after oral therapy [10]. Even without a total contract among research studies, the primary outcomes discovered the analysis showed that more youthful youngsters are more likely to demonstrate adverse

habits with a raise in treatment duration. Aminabadi et al supplied a structure within which to take into consideration the result of treatment duration on children with different ages [11]. Their findings showed a considerable destruction of actions in more youthful kids as therapy time was expanded.

Interestingly, it has been noted that treatment duration of patients with stress and anxiety or BMP is on typical 40% more than that of typical patients experiencing the same procedure [12]. Consequently, dentists should think about conditioning and progressive exposure to get collaboration in kids, and to keep their cooperation by making the therapy as short as possible. In addition, oral practitioners can embrace a time-out policy. Although the level of success of time-out differs, it appears to decrease patient disruptiveness in selected situations. On top of that, time-out duration and the regularity of time-out episodes are important factors to consider for its efficiency. The time-out ought to be short and only be used one or two times to get the appropriate habits in any given kid; or else, its failing is feasible [12].

Parental fear

Overall oral health of the kids has direct connection with Maternal oral overall health; not just did maternal dental stress and anxiety impact oral health of mothers however also various factors in during the growth of kids' dental anxiousness. The education program on mothers' oral health comprehension can be a target for renovation of the oral overall health of mothers and children [11]. Correct dental education and recognition programs have to be organized by dental experts to enhance the oral health knowledge and understanding of mothers and to reduce their fear for dental treatments, to ensure that their emotional aspects do not impact their kid's overall health.

Research studies were done by Khawja SG et al., Eitner S et al., and Pramila M et al. had done comparative evaluations and located a considerable relation between maternal anxiety and high cavities participation in their children [12-14]. These outcomes were like the explorations of today investigation. Milsom KM et al., in an examination of five-year-old children, located that oral tension in these kids was virtually associated with unforeseeable oral check outs, history of extrication, and having a dentally anxious parent [15]. Maternal education degree presumed a significant role in youngster's oral health and wellness. Mothers of high-education degree were

even more worried for their kid's oral health and wellness. In a study done by Tyagi U et al., the maternal effectiveness level is straight about the oral health and wellness condition of their kids ^[16].

Previous Dental and Medical Experiences and Frequency of Dental Visits

It has been stated that oral anxiousness is connected to previous dental experience. High degrees of oral anxiousness are anticipated amongst children on their first visit to the dental practitioner ^[13,17]. Oral stress and anxiety in children would certainly after that reduce with additional oral visits, thus having experienced more oral therapies ^[17]. Furthermore, this is perhaps due to the truth that previous dental experience develops a dentist-patient trust, and the youngsters end up being older and matured with subsequent oral checkups ^[17].

Kids who have experienced specific oral therapy will likely be less distressed about that treatment, and infrequent oral visits and long intervals in between visits have been located to be positively correlated with dental stress and anxiety ^{[17],[15]}. Conversely, Peretz B and Mann J, reported that dental anxiety in all children who have experienced oral procedures in the past is more than in youngsters that have not ^[18]. This could be due to the fact that the youngsters examined currently understood they would certainly have an undesirable dental session. In contrast, several researches stated that prior oral experience is not related to dental stress and anxiety and has no influence on it ^[19]. Extra unpleasant or invasive oral procedures will likely lead to unfavorable experience of dental therapy and the development of dental anxiousness ^[10]. On top of that, youngsters who had unfavorable experiences associated with clinical therapy and subjected to invasive clinical procedures have shown to be a lot more anxious concerning oral treatment.

Attachment influence on parental presence in operatory

There are still concerns and doubts regarding the effect of parental accompany throughout a youngster's therapy and its influence on habits of children. Even so, there are numerous evidences revealed that a youngster's actions are unaffected by the parental company or their lack in the dental operatory; however, the presence of mothers confirmed to be useful ^[20].

While there is an option to participate in the treatment process, parents tend to accompany in the oral operatory, it results from the close connection of children to their parents, and the exact same

attachment also makes the kid to look for parental existence. Peretz and Zadik done a research study on 104 parents completed a set of questions concerning their existence in the operatory. Most of the parents (70.2%) expressed a wish to be existing in the operatory ^[20]. Arathi and Ashwani also performed a set of questions research study responded to by 1350 parents and concluded that 78.3% of whom expressed their readiness to be existing with a child during dental treatments ^[21]. Crowley et al. researched the choice of parents of 8-year-old school children in Ireland in connection with accompanying their kids during dental treatments and ended that if given a selection, most of parents (67%) would certainly choose to accompany their youngster when getting oral therapy ^[22]. In the literature, it was showed that majority of Saudi parents studied preferred to stick with their youngsters throughout treatment ^[23].

• PATIENT ASSESSMENT

An examination of the child's eagerness to collaborate during the treatment process is crucial for therapy planning. There is no any analysis approach or tool that can exactly anticipate a patient's actions. However, there are multiple influence factors on a kid's response to treatment that can aid in treatment planning. Initial information can be collected from the parent through surveys concerning the child's cognitive degree, temperament/personality qualities, anxiousness and anxiety, response to complete strangers, and actions at previous medical/dental checkups, as well as exactly their expectations regarding child's response to future dental therapy ^[24]. Afterwards, the dental professional can assess the possibility of child's cooperative actions by observation of and communication with the patient. Whether the kid is approachable, rather reluctant, or timid and/or withdrawn may affect the success of numerous communicative methods. Analyzing the kid's growth, previous experiences, and current emotional state permits the dentist to develop an actions assistance plan to accomplish the necessary oral health care ^[25]. The dental practitioner must continue to be conscientious to physical and/or emotional indicators of stress and anxiety ^[26]. Adjustments in flexible behaviors might require changes to the behavior treatment plan.

There are numerous amounts of techniques used to gauge oral anxiousness in kids. Some relayed on determining physiologic indicators (as pulse rate), utilizing psychometric ranges, examining the youngster behavior throughout the oral visit (as FRS) or making use of projective method (as FIS). Kids habits assessed making use of Frankl's behavior rating

scale, which postures up to 93.4% sensitivity and has appropriate legitimacy reaching up to 77.8% [27].

Table 3. Frankel behavioral rating scale

Rating 1: DEFINITELY NEGATIVE: Refusal of treatment, crying forcefully, fearful, or any other overt evidence of extreme negativism.
Rating 2: NEGATIVE: Reluctant to accept treatment, uncooperative, some evidence of negative attitude but not pronounced i.e. sullen, withdrawn.
Rating 3: POSITIVE: Acceptance of treatment; at times caution. Willingness to comply with dentist, at time with reservation but patient follows the dentist's direction cooperatively.
Rating 4: DEFINITELY POSITIVE: Good rapport with the dentist, interested in the dental procedure, laughing and enjoying the situation

Youngsters self-rated scales were discovered to be extra precise than those rated by their parents [28]. The age of the participants in this research was in the series of 5 - 8 years, which called the preoperational stage. This stage is defined by growth of interest and cognitive capacities, which prepare children for appropriate social and social communication. As necessary, they came to be much more able to reveal themselves and more susceptible to be influenced by inspirational techniques [29]. The anxiousness level has been frequently assessed making use of the FIS, which was recognized for its high reproducibility, simplicity, and legitimacy for both medical and clinical purposes [30]. Research studies have revealed that FIS is a useful tool to examine oral anxiety also in extremely little ones [29]. The facial Image Scale (FIS) was created to assess the child's oral stress and anxiety right away prior to entering the oral clinic by using faces as an indicator of their sensations [31]. It contains five faces in a row ranging from delighted face to sad face. The range is scored by offering a worth of one to one of the most favorable face and 5 to the most negative face [29]. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Facial Image Scale (FIS) [29].

CONCLUSION:

Dental practitioners treating young children have the added responsibility of gaining their patient's cooperation to render the best treatment. Determinants that influence the development of a behavioral strategy for a young patient include disease status, the child's physical and mental development, parental characteristics, and provider personality and capabilities.

Oral practitioners dealing with young kids have the added duty of gaining their patient's assistance to make the best treatment. Components that influence the development of a behavioral technique for a young patient include disorder status, the child's physical and psychological development, parental features, and service provider individuality and capacities.

To provide even more humanized dental care, the prevalence of dental stress and anxiety should not be overlooked in scientific technique, specifically in pediatric dentistry. Methods for the analysis, avoidance, and control of dental anxiousness must be applied to enable far better therapy for kids, teenagers, and their parents. It is feasible to conduct a basic, effective examination of stress and anxiety in the regimen of a pediatric oral clinic with making use of verified devices. A sufficient method relating to kids and adolescents with oral anxiousness can aid in developing an excellent dental experience and a relying on relationship in between pediatric dental practitioners, patients, and parents.

Parents tension was the good predictor for children assistance in dental caring. Decrease mother's anxiousness for supplying the enough youngsters dental care. Father makes a lot more kids assistance, so fathers accompany is more efficient on youngsters well actions at oral care. It is recommend that father accompanying would certainly be among the services in youngster oral caring. Pain and negative experiences from dental therapy are taken into consideration significant factors for DFA and BMP. It is crucial that this be recognized by dental workers in order to prevent discomfort and discomfort.

REFERENCE:

1. Croll TP. The three-year-myth. *Pediatr Dent* 1987;9:86-7.

2. Klein H. Psychological effects of dental treatment on children of different ages. *J Dent Child* 1967;34:30-6.
3. Rud B, Kisling E. The influence of mental development on children's acceptance of dental treatment. *Scand J Dent Res* 1973;81:343-52.
4. Essau CA, Ollendick TH (editors). *The Wiley-Blackwell Handbook of the treatment of childhood and adolescent anxiety*. New Delhi: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.; 2013.
5. Liddell A, Gosse V. Characteristics of early unpleasant dental experiences. *J Behav Ther & Exp Psychiat*, 1998; 29:227-237.
6. Klingberg G. Dental anxiety and behaviour management problems in paediatric dentistry-a review of background factors and diagnostics. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent*, 2008; 9 (Suppl. 1):11-15.
7. McDonald RE, Avery DR, eds, *Dentistry for the Child and Adolescent*, 6th ed. Mosby, St Louis, 1994.
8. Saatchi M, Abtahi M, Mohammadi G, Mirdamadi M, Binandeh ES. The prevalence [15]of dental anxiety and fear in patients referred to Isfahan Dental School, Iran. *Dent Res J (Isfahan)*. 2015;12:248-53.
9. Rantavuori K, Lahti S, Hausen H, Seppä L, Kärkkäinen S. Dental fear and [34]oral health and family characteristics of Finnish children. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2004;62:207-13.
10. Taani DQ, El-Qaderi SS, Abu Alhaija ESJ. Dental anxiety in children and its relationship to dental caries and gingival condition. *Int J Dent Hyg*. 2005;3:83-87.
11. Aminabadi NA, Oskouei SG, Farahani RM. Dental treatment duration as an indicator of the behavior of 3-to 9-year-old pediatric patients in clinical dental settings. *J Contemp Dent Pract*. 2009;10(5):E025–32.
12. Getz T, Weinstein P. The effect of structural variables on child behavior in the operatory. *Pediatr Dent*. 1981;3(3):262–6.
13. Eitner S, Wichmann M, Paulsen A, Holst S. Dental anxiety--an epidemiological study on its clinical correlation and effects on oral health. *J Oral Rehabil* 2006;33:588-93.
14. Pramila M, Murthy AK, Chandrakala B, Ranganath S. Dental fear in children and its relation to dental caries and gingival condition - A cross sectional study in Bangalore city, India. *Int J Clin Dent Sci* 2010;1:1-5.
15. Milsom KM, Tickle M, Humphris GM, Blinkhorn AS. The relationship between anxiety and dental treatment experience in 5-year-old children. *Br Dent J* 2003; 194:503-6.
16. Tyagi U, Menon I, Tomar D, Singh A, Goyal J. Association between maternal oral health literacy and their preschoolers' oral health outcomes in Muradnagar -a cross-sectional study. *J Dent Specialities* 2017; 5:98-101.
17. Pekkan G, Kilicoglu A, Hatipoglu H. Relationship between dental anxiety, general anxiety level and depression in patients attending a university hospital dental clinic in Turkey. *Community Dent Health*. 2011; 28:149-53.
18. Peretz B, Mann J. Dental anxiety among Israeli dental students: a 4-year longitudinal study. *Eur J Dent Educ*. 2000; 4:133-37.
19. Humphris GM, Dyer TA, Robinson PG. The modified dental anxiety scale: UK general public population norms in 2008 with further psychometrics and effects of age. *BMC Oral Health*. 2009; 9:20.
20. Peretz B, Zadik D. Attitudes of parents towards their presence in the operatory during dental treatments to their children. *J Clin Pediatr Dent* 1998;23:27-30.
21. Arathi R, Ashwini R. Parental presence in the dental operatory-parent's point of view. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent* 1999;17:150-5.
22. Crowley E, Whelton H, O'Mullane D, Cronin M, Kelleher V, Flannery E, et al. Parents' preference as to whether they would like to accompany their child when receiving dental treatment – Results from a national survey. *J Ir Dent Assoc* 2005;51:23-4.
23. Abushal M, Adenubi JO. Attitudes of Saudi parents toward separation from their children during dental treatment. *Saudi Dent J* 2009;21:63-7.
24. Holst A, Hallonsten AL, Schroder U, Ek L, Edlund K. Prediction of behavior-management problems in 3- year-old children. *Scand J Dent Res* 1993;101(2):110-4.
25. American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. Policy on pediatric pain management. *Pediatr Dent* 2015;37(special issue):82-3.
26. Shonkoff JP, Garner AS. The lifelong effects of early childhood adversity and toxic stress. *Pediatrics* 2012;129: e232-46.
27. Asokan, S., Surendran, S., Punugoti, D., Nuvvula, S., & Priya, P. G. (2014). Validation of a novel behavior prediction scale: A two-center trial. *Contemporary Clinical Dentistry*, 5(4), 514–517.
28. Paglia, L., Gallus, S., de Giorgio, S., Cianetti, S., Lupatelli, E., Lombardo, G., Caruso, S. (2017). Reliability and validity of the Italian versions of the children's fear survey schedule-dental subscale and the modified child dental anxiety scale.

- European Journal of Paediatric Dentistry, 18(4), 305– 312.
29. Radhakrishna, S., Srinivasan, I., Setty, J., Krishna, M., Melwani, A., & Hegde, K. (2019). Comparison of three behavior modification techniques for management of anxious children aged 4-8 years. *Journal of Dental Anesthesia and Pain Medicine*, 19(1), 29– 36.
 30. Buchanan, H., & Niven, N. (2002). Validation of a facial image scale to assess child dental anxiety. *International Journal of Paediatric Dentistry*, 12(1), 47– 52.
 31. Buchanan H and Niven N. “Validation of a Facial Image Scale to assess child dental anxiety”. *International Journal of Paediatric Dentistry* 12.1 (2002): 47-52.
 32. Taani DQ, El-Qaderi SS, Abu Alhaija ESJ. Dental anxiety in children and its [35]
 33. relationship to dental caries and gingival condition. *Int J Dent Hyg*. 2005;3:83-87